

**MATEMATIKADA CHEKLI AYIRMALAR USULINI
O`RGANISHNING AHAMIYATI**

Eronov Omonboy

NDPI akademik litseyi matematika fani o`qituvchisi

Raximova Feruza

NDPI akademik litseyi matematika fani o`qituvchisi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10495065>

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada chekli ayirmalar usulining mohiyati ko`rsatib beriladi hamda ularning matematika va fizika sohasida masalalar yechishdagi ahmiyati tahlil etiladi.

Kalit so`zlar: chekli ayirma, matematika, hosila, fizika, markaziy ayirma.

Xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalarni taqribiy yechish usullaridan biri to`rlar usulidan foydalanib chegaraviy masalani yechish bilan tanishamiz. Bu usulning g`oyasiga ko`ra, masalan, soddalik uchun ikki o`zgaruvchili funksiya uchun o`lchami bir birlikli kvadrat sohada chegaraviy masalaning yechimini topish haqida tushunchalar kiritamiz. Aslida x va y koordinatalar bo`yicha to`r qadamlari har xil bo`lishi ham mumkin.

ASOSIY QISM

Ta`rifga ko`ra birinchi tartibli xususiy hosila quyidagicha yoziladi:

$$\frac{\partial u(x, y)}{\partial x} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{u(x + \Delta x, y) - u(x, y)}{\Delta x} \approx \frac{u(x + \Delta x, y) - u(x, y)}{\Delta x}$$

Agar $u(x, y)$ funksiyaning tadqiqot sohasi to`rining tugunlaridagina qarasaq, u holda birinchi tartibli xususiy hosilani ushbu

$$\frac{\partial u(x, y)}{\partial x} \approx \frac{u_{i+1, j} - u_{i, j}}{h}$$

o`ng chekli ayirma deb ataluvchi formula bilan yozishimiz mumkin, bu yerda (i, j) – tadqiqot sohasining (x, y) nuqtasiga mos keluvchi tugun. Bu formulaning bunday atalishiga sabab unda funksiyaning tadqiqot nuqtasi va undan o`ngdagi nuqtalardagi qiymatlaridan foydalanilganligida. Xuddi shunday tadqiqot nuqtasi va undan chapdagi nuqtadagi funksiya qiymatlaridan foydalansak, u holda ushbu

$$\frac{\partial u(x, y)}{\partial x} \approx \frac{u_{i, j} - u_{i-1, j}}{h}$$

chap chekli ayirma deb ataluvchi formulaga kelamiz.

Xuddi shunday, ikkinchi tartibli xususiy hosila uchun ushbu

$$\frac{\partial^2 u(x, y)}{\partial x^2} \approx \frac{u_{i+1,j} - 2u_{i,j} + u_{i-1,j}}{h^2}$$

markaziy chekli ayirma formulasini hosil qilamiz.

Bu formulalarda simmetrik nuqtalardagi funksiya qiymatlaridan foydalanildi. Umuman olganda, bu formulalar nosimmetrik nuqtalar uchun ham yozilishi mumkin (masalan, bir tomonlama chekli ayirmali hosilalar).

Parabolik tipdagi tenglamaga misol tariqasida ushbu

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$$

diffuziya tenglamasini qaraylik.

Bu tenglamani to`rlar usuli bilan yechish uchun to`rt nuqtali oshkor sxemadan foydalansak (1-rasm), quyidagi chekli ayirmali tenglamaga kelamiz:

$$u_{i,j+1} = D \frac{\tau}{h^2} (u_{i+1,j} - 2u_{i,j} + u_{i-1,j}) + u_{i,j}$$

Agar ushbu

$$\tau \leq \frac{h^2}{2D}$$

shart bajarilsagina bu oshkor ayirmali sxema ustivor bo`ladi. Chekli ayirmali tenglamadagi qavs oldidagi ifodani soddalik uchun k deb belgilaylik.

1-rasm. To`rt nuqtali oshkor sxema shabloni.

Bu masalani Mathcad matematik paketi yordamida sonli yechamiz (dasturda chekli ayirmali formuladagi qavs oldidagi ifoda a deb belgilash olingan, boshlang`ich shart $u(x,0) = \sin(x)$, chegaraviy shartlar esa nolga teng deb hisoblangan, ya`ni $u(0,t) = u(\pi,t) = 0$):

$$a := 0.02 \quad n := 30 \quad m := 50 \quad i := 0..n-1 \quad j := 1..m-1$$

$$u_{0,j} := \sin\left(\pi \cdot \frac{j}{m}\right) \quad u_{0,0} := 0 \quad u_{0,m} := 0$$

$$u_{i+1,j} := u_{i,j} + a \cdot (u_{i,j-1} + 2 \cdot u_{i,j} + u_{i,j+1})$$

Natijalarni grafiklar shaklida ifodalaylik (2-rasm):

2-rasm. Har xil vaqt momentlarida diffuziya jarayonining tarqalishi holati.

Rasmdan ko`rinib turibdiki, jarayon uzoqlashuvchi natijalarni berib bormoqda. Bunday kamchilikdan qutilish uchun oshkormas sxemadan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiq. Bunday oshkormas sxema deb atalishining sababi tadqiqot funksiyasining izlanayotgan qiymatlarini tenglamada vaqtning keyingi qatlamida topishda vaqtning oldingi qatladagi qiymatlari orqali oshkor ifodalab bo`lmasligida.

Quyidagi chegaraviy masalani qaraylik:

$$\rho c T_t = \lambda T_{xx}, \quad t > 0, 0 < x < l \quad T(0, t) = T_a; T(l, t) = T_b, \quad t > 0$$

$$T(x, 0) = T_0, \quad 0 < x < l$$

Bu chegaraviy masalaning analitik yechimi $u(x, t)$ oldindan ma`lum bo`lishi ham mumkin.

Tenglamadagi differensial operatorlarni ularning chekli-ayirmali analoglari bilan almashturamiz. Oshkormas sxemadan foydalanamiz (3-rasm).

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{T_i^{n+1} - T_i^n}{\tau}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} = \frac{T_{i+1}^{n+1} - 2T_i^{n+1} + T_{i-1}^{n+1}}{h^2}$$

Xususiy hosilalarni mos chekli ayirmalar bilan almashtirish natijasida quyidagi chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini hosil qilamiz:

$$\rho c \frac{T_i^{n+1} - T_i^n}{\tau} = \lambda \left(\frac{T_{i+1}^{n+1} - 2T_i^{n+1} + T_{i-1}^{n+1}}{h^2} \right), \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, N-1, n \geq 0 \quad (4.2)$$

Xususiy hosilalarni approksimatsiyalashning tanlangan sxemasini grafik ko`rinishda 3-rasmdagidek tasvirlash mumkin.

3- rasm foydalanilayotgan to`rt nuqtali oshkormas ayirmali sxemada yangi

4- vaqt qatlamida uchta nuqta va eski vaqt qatlamida esa bitta nuqta olinayotganini yaqqol ko`rsatadi.

3-rasm.To`rt nuqtali oshkormas sxema shabloni.

Hosilalarni bunday approksimatsiyalash uslubi oshkormas deb atalishiga sabab vaqtning yangi qatlamidagi temperaturalar maydoni oshkormas ifodalangan, ya`ni ularni aniqlash uchun berilgan tenglamalar sistemasini yechish zarur.

Hosil bo`lgan tenglamalar sistemasini plastinkalarning ichki tugun nuqtalari uchun quyidagicha umumiy ko`rinishga keltirish mumkin:

$$A_i \cdot T_{i+1}^{n+1} - B_i \cdot T_i^{n+1} + C_i \cdot T_{i-1}^{n+1} = F_i \quad (4.3)$$

bu yerda

$$A_i = C_i = \frac{\lambda}{h^2}, \quad B_i = \frac{2\lambda}{h^2} + \frac{\rho c}{\tau}, \quad F_i = -\frac{\rho c}{\tau} T_i^n$$

Bunday tenglamalar ikkinchi tartibli uch nuqtali deb ataladi.(4.3) sistema uch diagonally tuzilmaga ega.

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